

NATURE MUSEUMS (ECOMUSEUM), NATURE PARKS (BOTANY, ZOO) AND PEOPLE'S ACTIVITY, THEIR OPINION

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Abstract. *The research was carried out in the form of a questionnaire, for five days, using the "Telegram" messenger. According to the results of the survey, 633 people read the questionnaires, but more than 216 people (34 %) actively answered the questions. 66 % (417 people) read the questions but did not want to answer not actively.*

Key words: *Museums of nature, Ecological culture, Zoo, State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan, Tashkent Botanical Garden, Tourism.*

1. Introduction

The concept of eco museum was created after Second World War when many traditional communities were torn apart, heritage places were destroyed and habits began to change. To conclude, there are numerous definitions of Eco museums. All of them contain common elements which are as follows: • community, • heritage, • sustainability, • location [1, 2]. Eco museums help people closer to nature. It allows better understanding the laws of nature, and also helps to form ecological culture in the minds of the young generation. Eco museums are to be conceived and designed by publicly accountable institutions and by local inhabitants; they should be jointly maintained and be an instrument for shared interests [3]. Eco museums act as a window to nature for the population [4]. Ecological museums bring people closer to nature, develop tourism, preserve natural resources, and clearly show the impact of the human factor on nature [5]. How often people go to ecological museums and do not go to them, it shows people's ecological culture and ecological knowledge.

2. Method

The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for one week, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 633 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 34 % (216 people) answered the questions. 66 % (417 people) of those who read the questionnaire did not answer the questionnaire questions.

Figure 1. Active (34 %) and inactive (66 %)

3. Results

Answers to survey questions were also put into diagrams and analyzed. 223 people answered the first question called, and the results were represented by the following diagram (Figure 2). The first question was: «Have you been to the State Nature Museum of Uzbekistan? »

Figure 2.

The second question of the survey, that is, "Do you enjoy traveling to nature, eco-museums?" and 203 people answered the question and the answers can be found in the diagram below (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The third question of the survey, that is, "Have you been to Tashkent Botanical Garden?" and 214 people answered the question and the results of the analysis are represented by diagram (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

The fourth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "Have you been to Tashkent Zoo?" and 221 people answered the question, and these answers are represented by diagram (Figure 5).

Figure 5.

The fifth question of the anonymous survey "Do you encourage others (for example, your children, siblings) to visit Zoos, Botanical gardens, Nature parks more often?" and 221 people answered the question, and the results are illustrated by diagram (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

4. Discussion

According to the first question of the anonymous questionnaire, most of the respondents (61%) did not visit the State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan. However, the majority of participants (74%) indicated that they would like and enjoy traveling to Eco museums. 50% of the respondents said that they visited the Tashkent Botanical Garden. Also, 56% of the respondents said that they had visited the Tashkent Zoo. A significant share of the participants (69%) said that they always support their relatives (children, friends and others) visiting eco-museums and parks.

5. Conclusion

Analyzing the results of the questionnaire, it can be seen that the population has a high interest and desire to visit ecological museums and nature parks. The majority of our population supports their relatives to go to nature parks and eco-parks. From this it can be concluded that the majority of people of our modern society want to go to Eco parks and Nature museums and they want to support creating many of them.

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